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Research Article

Evaluation Of Anti-Inflammation & Memory Enhancing Activity For Some Pharmacological Active Extracts

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ABSTRACT

It can be stated that the ethanolic extract has beneficial effects in long lasting in membrane stabilizing method, inhibition of protein denaturation method and proteinase model. It also showed a protective effect on inflammation and memory enhancing effect. The mechanism may be mediated via the inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis in acute inflammatory reaction as well as inhibition of various lysosomal enzymes in chronic inflammatory responses this, justifies the claim made by Siddha and Ayurveda. The mechanism for the memory enhancing activity may be inhibition of cholinesterase enzymes in brain. Besides from the obvious therapeutic importance, these ethanolic extract of selected whole plant materials would be useful in understanding the mechanism of diseases with higher levels of cellular and molecular level. These methanolic extract could serve as lead molecules for development of prospective anti-inflammatory and memory enhancing agents. Further detailed studies are required to elucidate the exact mechanism based on molecular and genetic level responsible for activity. The present findings are significant for the development of alternative, inexpensive and perhaps safer strategies for the treatment of diseases. A detailed study is also required on isolation, characterization and in vivo study.

INTRODUCTION

The use of herbal medicines continues to expand rapidly across the world. Many countries now turn towards herbal medicines or herbal products for their health care in national health-care settings. According to WHO, 80% if the rural population in developing countries depend on traditional medicines to meet their primary health care needs (1). Authentication and standardization are

prerequisite steps while considering source materials for herbal formulation in any system of medicine (2). In traditional systems of medicine, the drugs are primarily dispensed as water decoction or ethanol extract. Fresh plant parts, juice, or crude powders are a rarity rather than a rule. Thus medicinal plant parts should be authentic and free from harmful materials like pesticides, heavy metals, microbial or radioactive

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contamination, etc. (3). It is very important that a system of standardization should establish for every plant medicine in the market because the scope for variation in different batches of medicine is enormous. World Health Organization (WHO) encourages, recommends, and promotes traditional / herbal remedies in national health care programmes because these drugs are safe, people have faith in them and easily available at low cost. The WHO is continuously emphasizing to ensure quality control of medicinal plant products by using modern techniques and applying suitable standards (4). India has a rich heritage of traditional medicine constituting with its different components like Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, Homoeopathy and naturopathy. Traditional health care has been flourishing in this country for many centuries (5). The growing use of botanicals by the public is forcing moves to evaluate the health claims of these agents and to develop standards of quality and manufacture. Various traditional medicine systems, especially Indian system of medicine attracted the global attention due to their long historical clinical use and reliable therapeutic efficacy. Many big pharmaceutical companies are using traditional medicine as an excellent pool for discovering natural bioactive compounds.

MATERIAL & METHODS-

The whole plant parts of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy() were purchased from the local Aria and also collected from Govt.Ayurvedic College(Medicinal Garden) Gwalior Madhya Pradesh .

Preparation of total crude extract

Whole plant materials were dried under shade and subjected to coarse powder for extraction process. Accurately weighed quantity of whole plant material was extracted using 95 % ethanol by soxhlet apparatus for 72 h. The ethanolic extracts were dried under the reduced pressure to get crude methanolic extracts. The ethanolic extracts were dried completely under reduced pressure. After

drying, the respective extracts were weighed and percentage yield was determined.

Preliminary phytochemical tests

Qualitative chemical tests of ethanolic extracts were subjected to various chemical tests to detect various phytoconstituents.

Test for Alkaloids: -

Dragendorff's test: - To the extract add Dragendorff's reagent, reddish brown precipitate indicates presence of alkaloids.

Wagner's test: - To the extract add Wagner's reagent, reddish brown precipitate indicates presence of alkaloids.

Hager's test: - To the extract add Hager's reagent, yellow precipitate indicates presence of alkaloids.

Test for Amino acids:-

Millon's test: - To the extract add about 2ml of Millon's reagent white precipitate indicates presence of amino acids.

Ninhydrine test: - To the extract add Ninhydrine solution, boil, violet colour indicates presence of amino acid.

Test for Flavonoids: -

Shinoda test: - To the extract add few magnesium turnings and concentrated hydrochloric acid dropwise, pink scarlet, crimson red or occasionally green to blue colour appears after few minutes.

Alkaline reagent test: - To the extract add few drops of sodium hydroxide solution, intense yellow colour is formed which turns to colorless on addition of few drops of dilute acid indicate presence of flavonoids.

Test for Phenolics compounds (Tannins):-

Ferric chloride test: - Treat the extract with ferric chloride solution, blue colour appears if hydrolysable tannins are present and green colour appears if condensed tannins are present.

Phenazone test: - Add about 0.5 gm of sodium acid phosphate to 5ml of extract warm it and filter. To the filtrate add 2% phenazone solution, bulky precipitate is formed, which is often colored.

Gelatin test: -To the extract add 1% gelatin solution containing 10% sodium chloride. Precipitate is formed.

Test for Proteins: -

Biuret test: - To the extract (2ml) add Biuret reagent (2ml), violet colour indicates presence of proteins.

Hydrolysis test: - Hydrolyze the extract with hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid. Then carry out the Ninhydrine test for amino acids.

Test for Steroids and Triterpenoids: -

Libermann-Burchard test: - Treat the extract with few drops of acetic anhydride, boil and cool. Then add concentrated sulphuric acid from the side of the test tube, brown ring is formed at the junction two layers and upper layer turns green which shows presence of steroids and formation of deep red colour indicates presence of triterpenoids.

Salkowski test: -Treat the extract with few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid red colour at lower layer indicates presence of steroids and formation of yellow coloured lower layer indicates presence of triterpenoids.

Test for Carbohydrates: -

Molish's test: -To the extract add few drops of alcoholic α -naphthol, then add few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid through sides of test tube, purple to violet colour ring appears at the junction.

Fehling's test: - Mix 1 ml Fehling's A and 1 ml Fehling's B solutions, boil for 1 min. add equal volume of test solution. Heat in boiling water bath for 5-10 min. first a yellow, then brick red precipitate is observed.

Benedict's test: -Mix equal volume of Benedict's reagents and test solution in test tube. Heat in boiling water bath for 5 min. solution appears green, yellow or red depending upon amount of reducing sugars present in test solution.

Test for Anthraquinone glycosides: -

Borntrager's test: - Boil the test material with 1ml of sulphuric acid in a test tube for 5minutes.

Filter while hot. Cool the filtrate and shake with equal volume of dichloromethane or chloroform. Separate the lower layer of dichloromethane or chloroform and shake it with half of its volume of dilute ammonia. A rose pink to red colour is produced in the ammonical layer.

Modified Borntrager's test: - Boil 200mg of the test material with 2ml of dilute sulphuric acid. Treat it with 2ml of 5% aqueous ferric chloride solution (freshly prepared) for 5 minutes, shake it with equal volume of chloroform and continue the test as above. As some plants contain anthracene aglycone in a reduced form, if ferric chloride is used during the extraction, oxidation to Anthraquinone takes place, which shows response to Borntrager's test.

Test for Coumarin glycosides: -

Place a small amount of sample in test tube and cover the test tube with a filter paper moistened with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. Place the covered test tube on water bath for several minutes. Remove the paper and expose it to ultraviolet (UV) light, the paper shows green fluorescence

Test for Saponin glycosides: -

Froth formation test: -Place 2ml solution of drug in water in a test tube, shake well, stable froth (foam) is formed.

Test for Cardiac glycosides: -

Keller-killiani test (test for deoxy sugars): - Extract the drug with chloroform and evaporate it to dryness. Add 0.4ml of glacial acetic acid containing trace amount of ferric chloride. Transfer to a small test tube; add carefully 0.5ml of concentrated sulphuric acid by the side of the test tube. Acetic acid layer shows blue colour.

Legal's test: - Treat the extract with pyridine and add alkaline sodium nitroprusside solution, blood red colour appears.

Baljet's test: - Treat the extract with picric acid or sodium picrate, orange colour is formed.

Anti-Inflammatory Activity

Membrane Stabilizing Activity Of Methanolic Extract

The human red blood cells (HRBC) membrane stabilization had been used as a method to study anti-inflammatory activity. In this method, blood was collected from healthy human volunteers who had not been taken anti-inflammatory drug for 2 weeks prior to the experiments. This blood was mixed with equal volume of sterilized alsever solution (2 % dextrose, 0.8% sodium citrate, 0.5% citric acid and 0.42% sodium chloride). The blood was centrifuged at 3000 rpm and packed cells were washed with isosaline and a 10% suspension was made with iso saline. Various concentrations of test samples (F1- F6) in concentration of

protection was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Protection} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

Inhibition Of Protein Denaturation Method

The ethanolic extract of selected plant materials were suspended in distilled water. The following procedure was followed for evaluating the percent of inhibition of protein denaturation: -

Control solution (50 ml) consists of 2ml of Egg albumin (from fresh hen's egg) and 28 ml of phosphate buffer (PBS, pH 6.4) and 20ml distilled water.

Standard drug (50 ml) consists of 2ml of Egg albumin and 28 ml of phosphate buffer and 20 ml of various concentrations of standard drug Diclofenac sodium (20, 40, 60, 80 & 100 µg/ml).

Test solution (50 ml) consists of 2ml of Egg albumin and 28 ml of phosphate buffer and 20 ml of various concentrations of methanolic extract in a concentration of 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 µg/ml. All of the above reaction mixtures were adjusted to pH 6.4, using a small amount of 1N HCl. The samples were incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes and heated at 70°C for 5 minutes. After cooling, the absorbance of the above solutions was

measured using UV- spectrophotometer at 660 nm. The percent inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated using the following formula (57, 58).

Proteinase Inhibitory Activity

The methanolic extract of whole plant materials were suspended in distilled water.

The following procedure was followed for evaluating the Proteinase Inhibitory Activity.

Control solution (50 ml) 20 ml consists of 0.06 mg Trypsin, 10 ml 20mM Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.4) and 10 ml distilled water.

Standard drug (50 ml) 20 ml consists of 0.06 mg Trypsin, 10 ml 20mM Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.4) and 10 ml of various concentrations of standard drug Diclofenac sodium. (20, 40, 60, 80 & 100 µg/ml).

Test solution (50 ml) 20 ml consists of 0.06 mg Trypsin, 10 ml 20mM Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.4) and 10 ml of various concentrations of methanolic extract in a concentration of 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 µg/ml. All the reactions were incubated at 37° C for 5 minutes and then 10 ml of 0.8% (w/v) casein was added. Again the samples were incubated for an additional 20 min and 10 ml of 70% perchloric acid was added to arrest the reaction. Cloudy suspension was centrifuged and the absorbance of the supernatant was read at 210 nm against buffer as blank. The experiment was performed as triplicate. The percent inhibition of proteinase inhibitory activity was calculated (59).

Memory Enhancing Activity Determination of Acetylcholinesterase Inhibitory Activity.

AChE activity was measured using a modified 96-well microplate assay (11) based on Ellman's method (21). The enzyme hydrolyses the substrate acetylthiocholine resulting in the product thiocholine which reacts with Ellman's reagent (DTNB) to produce 2- nitrobenzoate-5- mercaptothiocholine and 5-thio-2-nitrobenzoate which can be detected at 412 nm. 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0 was used as a buffer throughout the

experiment unless otherwise stated. AChE used in the assay was from electric eel (type VI-S lyophilized powder, 518 U/mg solid, 844 U/mg protein). The enzyme stock solution (518 U/ml) was kept at 280uC. The further enzyme-dilution was done in 0.1% BSA in buffer. DTNB was dissolved in the buffer containing 0.1 M NaCl and 0.02 M MgCl₂. ATCI was dissolved in deionized water. In the 96-well plates, 100 ml of 3 mM DTNB, 20 ml of 0.26 U/ml of AChE, and 40 ml of buffer (50 mM tris pH 8.0), 20 ml of extract in various concentrations (25, 50, 100, 250 and 500 mg/ml) dissolved in buffer containing not more than 10% methanol were added to the wells. After mixing, the plate was incubated for 15 min (25uC) and then the absorbance was measured at 412 nm in Tecan infinite 200 microplate reader and the readings were used as blank. The enzymatic reaction was initiated by the addition of 20 ml of 15 mM ATCI and the hydrolysis of

acetylthiocholine was monitored by reading the absorbance every 5 min for 20 min. Physostigmine was used as positive control. All the reactions were performed in triplicate. The percentage inhibition was calculated as follows

$$\text{Percentage Inhibition} = (E - S) / E \times 100$$

Where

E₀ is the activity of the enzyme without extract

S is the activity of enzyme with the extract.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION-

Extractive value determination

Dried whole plant material of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy were extracted by ethanol. The percentage yields of all dried extracts were determined by using the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Extract}}{\text{Weight of powder drug Taken}} \times 100$$

TableNo.1: Different extracts with their appearance and % yield (in gm)

S. No.	Extracts	Color of dried extracts	Consistency of dried extracts	% Yield (W/W)
1	<i>Convolvulus pluricaulis</i> Choisy (Ethanolic extract)	Dark Green	Dried Powder	11 %

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The preliminary phytochemical analysis revealed that different active constituent present in different

extracts such as carbohydrates, proteins, amino acids, fat, oils, steroids, terpenoids, glycosides, alkaloids, tannins and other phenolics compounds.

Table No 2: Qualitative chemical analysis of extracts by chemical tests

S. No	Phytoconstituents	Chemical Tests	<i>Convolvulus pluricaulis</i> Choisy
1	Alkaloids	Wagner's test	+
		Dragendorff's test	+
		Mayer's test	+
		Hager's test	-
2	Amino Acid	Millon's test	+
		Ninhydrine test	-
3	Flavonoids	Shinoda test	+
		Alkaline reagent test	+
		Zinc hydrochloridetest	-
4	Phenolics(Tannins)	Gelatin test	+
		Phenazone test	-
		Ferric chloride test	+
5	Protein	Biuret test	+
		Hydrolysis test	+

		Test with trichloroacetic acid	-
6	terpenoids & Steroids	Libermann- Burchard test	+
		Salkowski test	+
7	Carbohydrates	Benedict's test	+
		Fehling's test	+
		Molish's test	-
8	nthaquinoneglycosides	Borntrager's test	+
		Modified Borntrager's test	+
9	Coumaringlycosides		-
10	Saponin glycosides		+
11	Cardiac glycosides	Baljet's test	+
		Legal's test	+
		Keller-killiani test	+

**Where, (-) Negative, (+) Positive
Thin layer chromatographic studies of bioactive extracts**

TLC study has shown the presence of different components present in ethanolic extract of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy when the extract

were run in specific solvent system. Before reaching to most optimum solvent system a number of systems were employed.

TLC of methanolic extract of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy

Table No 3: Summary of TLC

S No.	Extract	Solvent systems	Detecting reagents	Color	No. of spots	value of Spots
1	Methanolic	Ethyl acetate: methanol: water (77:18:05)	Vanillin sulphuric acid, heated at 110°C for 5 Min.	Green & orange	5	0.23, 0.32, 0.61, 0.72, 0.81

Figure No. 2: TLC of ethanolic extract

Membrane Stabilizing Activity of Extracts on Rat Erythrocytes

The ethanolic extract was analyzed by membrane stabilizing property at concentration range of 100-500 µg/ml. Ethanolic extract significantly protect the rat erythrocyte membrane against lysis induced by hypotonic solution. At a concentration of 500 µg/ml, the extract produced 72.60% protection of RBC haemolysis as compared with 73.84% produced by prednisolone.

Table No. 3: Membrane stabilizing activity of extract at different concentration

S. No.	Fractions	Concentration (µg/ml)	% Protection
1	Control	----	100
2	Prednisolone	100 µg/ml	73.84
3	Ethanolic Extract	100 µg/ml	54.54
		200 µg/ml	57.95
		300 µg/ml	65.90
		400 µg/ml	68.18
		500 µg/ml	72.60

Protein Denaturation Methods

The ethanolic extract of selected plant showed 40.22% inhibition. The Diclofenac sodium

showed 48.50% inhibition against denaturation of protein. The results are summarized in Table No. 4.

Table No. 4: Effect of ethanolic extract on Protein Denaturation.

S. No.	Treatment	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	% Inhibition
1	Control	----	---
2	Ethanolic Extract	100	18.23
		200	19.98
		300	28.42
		400	34.53
		500	40.22
3	Diclofenac Sodium	20	21.50
		40	30.55
		60	40.75
		80	48.50

Proteinase inhibitory action:

The ethanolic extract of selected plant materials showed 42.65% inhibition respectively.

The Diclofenac sodium showed 63.89% inhibition against proteinase inhibitory activity.

Table No. 5: Effect of ethanolic extract on proteinase inhibitory activity

S. No.	Treatment	concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	% Inhibition
1	Control	----	-----
2	Ethanolic Extract	100	19.20
		200	25.60
		300	31.10
		400	37.50
		500	42.65
3	Diclofenac Sodium	20	26.88
		40	32.50
		60	41.55
		80	50.50
		100	63.89

Acetylcholinesterase Inhibitory Activity of the Extracts

The ethanolic extracts of selected plant material used in Ayurveda for nervous system disorders were tested for AChE inhibitory activity using Ellman's colorimetric method in 96-welled microplate. The inhibition curves have been

presented in Table 5 representing the % inhibition at 100 mg/ml and IC₅₀ for extracts. Physostigmine was used as the standard AChE inhibitor in this study which showed IC₅₀ of 0.07560.003 mg/ml. IC₅₀ for AChE inhibitory activity was 7763.1 mg/ml respectively. The plant showed very high antioxidant activity also in the DPPH assay.

Table No. 5: % Inhibition and IC₅₀ values of ethanolic plant extracts AChE inhibition assays

S. No.	% Inhibition of DPPH at 0.1 mg/ml	IC ₅₀ for DPPH scavenging assay (mg/ml)	IC ₅₀ for AChE inhibition assay (mg/ml)	% AChE inhibition at 0.1 mg/ml
1.	86±9.6	54.56±7.2	77±6.2	62.46±5.3

DISCUSSION

Tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) is known to play a critical role in the pathogenic mechanisms of RA, and is now targeted in the standard treatment of patients with RA. Interleukin-1 (IL-1) is well established as another key pro-inflammatory cytokine involved in RA. Recently, macrophage migration inhibitory factor (MIF) has been considered to have pro-inflammatory effects in RA. MIF is implicated in leukocyte recruitment, activation, proliferation and survival, as well as the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and mediators, and mechanisms of bone and cartilage injury, all of which contribute to the pathology of inflammation (60). Herbal medicines derived from plant extracts are being increasingly utilized to treat a wide variety of diseases, although relatively modest acquaintance about their mode of action is existing. There is an emergent interest in the pharmacological evaluation of various plants used in Indian traditional systems of medicine. Thus, in the present investigation, an attempt was made to evaluate the anti-inflammatory and memory enhancing activity of selected medicinal plants (*Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy) on the basis of ayurveda and their traditional uses in a suitable experimental in vitro model. In the preliminary study, dried powders of all selected plant were extracted by using methanol. The extracts were dried and screened for the presence of various active constituents. The extracts showed the presence of alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenolic compounds, tannins, steroids and fatty acids. For the preliminary assessment, the plant extract was evaluated by in-vitro models for anti-inflammatory and memory enhancing activity. Bioactive extract was then tested chemically to know the presence of different chemical constituents. TLC studies were also performed to know the number of constituents present in both the fractions and to establish finger print profile. In the present investigation,

phytochemical screening showed the presence of steroids, terpenoids, tannins, flavonoids, glycoside. Cellular filtration is the main key aspect of inflammatory response and leukocytes play very important role in this infiltration process. During the process of inflammation, these cells release their lysosomal contents such as bactericidal enzymes and proteases causing further tissue damage and inflammation (61, 62). Such injury to cell membrane will further render the cell more susceptible to secondary damage through free radical induced by lipid peroxidation. The physical property of the cell membrane is controlled by specific membrane proteins and they contribute to the regulation of the volume and water content of cells by controlling the movement of sodium and potassium ions (61, 63). Since the RBC membrane is similar to that of lysosomal membrane, inhibition of RBC hemolysis will therefore, provide good insights into the inflammatory process especially as both events are also consequent of injury. Injury to lysosomal membrane usually triggers the release of phospholipases A2 that mediates the hydrolysis of phospholipids to produce inflammatory mediators. Stabilization of the membranes of these cells inhibits lysis and subsequent release of the cytoplasmic contents which in turn limits the tissue damage and exacerbation of the inflammatory response (61). It is therefore expected that compounds with membrane stabilization activity should offer significant protection of cell membrane against injurious substances. Exposure of red blood cell to ruinous substances such as hypotonic medium and phenyl hydrazine results in lysis of its membrane accompanied by haemolysis and oxidation of hemoglobin (64). The hemolytic effect of hypotonic solution is associated to excessive accumulation of fluid inside the cell, consequential in the rupturing of its membrane and they are also sensitive to damage through free radicals induced

by lipid peroxidation. In our study, In vitro assessments of the effect of extract of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy on membrane stabilization showed that it inhibited heat and hypo tonicity induced lysis of red blood cells. Ethanolic extract at higher concentration showed 71.59 % at a concentration of 500 µg/ml protection. It is already reported that NSAIDs with membrane stabilizing properties are well known for their activity with the early phase of the pro-inflammatory mediators and stabilizing cellular membranes, which reduces tissue damage and pain.

CONCLUSION-

In the present investigation, the ability of ethanolic extract to inhibit protein denaturation as well as protienase inhibitory were studied. The ethanolic extract of *Convolvulus pluricaulis* Choisy were found to be effective in inhibiting heat induced albumin denaturation & protienase inhibition at different concentrations. The inhibition of denaturation and protienase may be probable mechanism of ethanolic extract as anti-inflammatory activity. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is a key enzyme in the cholinergic nervous system. Therapies designed to reverse the cholinergic deficit in AD is mostly based on inhibitors of AchE, which enhance cholinergic transmission with modest and transient therapeutic effects. Several studies revealed that cholinesterase inhibitors could act on multiple therapeutic targets such as prevention of the formation of b-amyloid plaques, antioxidant activity.

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